

Impacts of intermittency on low-temperature electrolysis technologies: A comprehensive review

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ABSTRACT

By offering promising solutions to two critical issues – the integration of renewable energies into energy systems and the decarbonization of existing hydrogen applications – green hydrogen production through water electrolysis is set to play a crucial role in addressing the major challenges of the energy transition. However, the successful integration of renewable energy sources relies on gaining accurate insights into the impacts that intermittent electrical supply conditions induce on electrolyzers. Despite the rising importance of addressing intermittency issues to accelerate the widespread adoption of renewable energy sources, the state-of-the-art lacks research providing an in-depth understanding of these concerns. This paper endeavors to offer a comprehensive review of existing research, focusing on proton exchange membrane (PEM) and alkaline electrolysis technologies operating under intermittent operation. Despite growing interest over the last ten years, the review underscores the scarcity of industrial-scale databases for quantifying these impacts.

1. Introduction

Growing energy demand and environmental concerns related to greenhouse gas (GHG) emission are increasingly shifting the energy industry towards the use of renewable energy sources [1,2]. As sustainable and clean sources, renewable energies hold very strong assets in the context of the energy transition [3]. However, the integration of renewable energy sources into electrical grids is challenging due to their intermittent and unpredictable nature. As a result, intermittency turns into a major issue for electricity suppliers who need dispatchable sources and predictable quantities of electricity available at all times, in order to always be able to consistently match energy demand. Energy storage holds significant importance in addressing issues related to grid stability and maximizing the potential of renewable energy sources. Whether employed as a feedstock or an energy carrier, hydrogen serves as a means to store energy from intermittent renewable sources. This stored energy can then be harnessed for various applications such as mobility, infrastructure, industrial processes etc. Additionally, it serves as a compelling energy carrier for remote communities without access to a connected grid, reducing reliance on imports and enhancing energy supply stability [4]. In short, the growing interest in hydrogen stems from its diverse applications, the variety of processes and sources for its

production and its important foreseen contribution in decarbonizing the future energy system. Although hydrogen definitely provides attractive solutions in the current energy context, a great deal of research still needs to be carried out regarding production processes. Currently, 95 % of hydrogen is produced from fossil fuels, by steam reforming of natural gas, or extracted from other hydrocarbons, resulting in the formation of carbon dioxide emissions and airborne pollutants [5]. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), hydrogen production alone accounted for the generation of 830 million metric tons of CO₂ per year, contributing to global CO₂ emissions of 2–3 %. Other hydrogen production processes in use or under development involve water electrolysis using electricity sourced from renewable energy sources. While the total capacity of installed electrolyzers currently stands at approximately 460 MW, the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) projects that this capacity must surge to 350 GW by 2030 to meet the ambitious target of limiting the temperature rise to 1.5 °C [6]. Integrating renewable energy sources into the operation of electrolyzers offers a highly promising solution for addressing two main issues: the smooth integration of renewable energies into electrical grids and the decarbonization of current hydrogen production pathways. Nonetheless, the intermittent nature of renewable energies induces load fluctuations, and affects the electrolyzer key performance indicators at all levels of the system operation. Barbir et al. [7] were the first authors to

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Abbreviations

AEM	Anion Exchange Membrane
AST	Accelerated Stress Test
ATEX	Explosive Atmosphere
BG	Bond Graph
BoP	Balance-of-Plant
CCM	Catalyst Coated Membrane
CL	Catalyst Layer
CNLS	Complex Non-linear Least Square
EEC	Equivalent Electrical Circuit
EIS	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
GDL	Gas Diffusion Layer
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HER	Hydrogen Evolution Reaction
HFR	High Frequency Resistance
HHV	High Heating Value
HTO	Hydrogen Transferred to Oxygen

IEA	International Energy Agency
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
JRC	Joint Research Center
LEL	Low Explosivity Limit
LFR	Low Frequency Resistance
LHV	Low Heating Value
MEA	Membrane Electrode Assembly
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
OER	Oxygen Evolution Reaction
OTH	Oxygen Transferred to Hydrogen
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane
PGM	Platinum Group Metal
PTL	Porous Transport Layer
PV	Photovoltaics
RF	Ripple Factor
SOE	Solid Oxide Electrolysis
STEM	Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy
TPB	Triple Phase Boundary

put forward a theoretical vision on the issues arising from intermittency and resulting impacts on the efficiency and durability of PEM electrolyzers when integrated with a photovoltaic (PV) power plant in different setups. More recent reviews addressing intermittency issues related to “renewable electrolyzers” have been identified. For instance, Tao et al. [8] discussed the opportunities, limitations and technical challenges related to the scale-up and direct coupling of intermittent PV and wind energy sources to electrolyzers. Brauns et al. [9] focused their review on alkaline technology, offering an objective analysis of the main challenges associated with using renewable energies, regarding the purity level of the product gas and performance degradation. Besides, they provided approaches for optimizing the design and operation of alkaline electrolyzers to improve their performance when powered with renewable and intermittent energy sources. Lopez et al. [10] delved into the challenges driven by the integration PV plants into the operation of alkaline, PEM, and anion exchange membrane (AEM) electrolyzers. They particularly emphasized the issues related to part-load operation and the difficulties in effectively managing the various scales of dynamic responses of an electrolyzer during intermittent operation. Kojima et al. [11] offered a wider perspective on intermittency issues across all electrolysis technologies, by providing factual insights from the literature and placing a strong focus on durability and degradation issues. Sayed et al. [12] compiled the key mechanisms outlined in the scientific literature regarding the effects of dynamic operation on PEM technology, incorporating both technical and economic perspectives and scoping their analysis to the cell and stack operational scales. However, so far, no specific work has been done to gather all the knowledge available regarding quantitative assessments of the intermittency impacts from the cell/stack to the full system level.

This paper aims at counterbalancing this lack of feedback. First, we provide a comprehensive review on the impacts of intermittency related to the operation of alkaline and PEM electrolyzers, being the two most mature electrolysis technologies to date. Second, we give a classification of 130 relevant experimental and modelling studies identified from the year 2000–2023 and categorized by technology, operational scale, and performance indicator. Fig. 1 depicts a significant surge in interest in the subject, particularly since 2010, with only nine relevant publications identified between 2000 and 2008. Moreover, the state-of-the-art highlights a growing interest in PEM technology, particularly from 2016 onwards.

The review addresses intermittency issues across various operational scales, ranging from the cell level to the entire system, and focusing on key performance indicators pertinent to alkaline and PEM electrolyzers when operating under intermittent conditions. Gas purity, efficiency

Fig. 1. Classification of the reviewed publications from 2000 to 2023.

and durability have been identified as the most critical indicators, as they are significantly impacted by intermittent load conditions. Furthermore, it is important to note that this review focuses exclusively on PEM and alkaline technologies, universally recognized as more mature. Specific issues related to non-conventional electrolysis, such as decoupled technologies, anion exchange membrane (AEM), and high-temperature electrolysis (including solid oxide electrolysis (SOE), proton-conducting, molten carbonate, etc.), are not addressed. Additionally, the decision to conduct a combined review of alkaline and PEM electrolysis is grounded in the shared similarities between these technologies regarding their effects to intermittency. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that the physical mechanisms driving the effects of intermittent operation on each technology exhibit different trends. Moreover, the primary goal of the review is to present a broad overview of the impact of intermittency on key performance indicators, rather than delving into the intricate physical mechanisms underlying these effects.

The initial step of this methodology involved a delineation of the scope for the keywords “performance indicators” and “intermittency” relevant to the core topic of this review. The considerations arising from this analysis provided the framework for structuring the review, which encompasses (i) introducing the concept of intermittency, (ii) examining the methodologies employed to assess system performance, and (iii) summarizing the significant literature learnings related to intermittency impacts. While numerous publications discuss the technical challenges of integrating low-temperature electrolyzers with intermittent energy sources, the key figures of this review indicates a prevailing trend of

limited quantitative studies based on the application of operational intermittent profiles. Furthermore, the review shows that the methods and materials currently used are reasonably well balanced, with a slight inclination towards experiments, although a significant portion of the identified publications combine both experimental and modelling approaches in a complementary manner. However, Fig. 2a showcases that 74 % of the reported publications focus on lab-scale (cell and stack level) or small-scale system-based investigations, while only 26 % of the remaining publications delve into commercial pilot or system-scale demonstrators.

The distribution of the three key performance indicators exhibits notable variations depending on the technology, as depicted in Fig. 2b. Overall, literature emphasizes alkaline electrolyzers over PEM, suggesting a preference for alkaline technology in intermittent operation scenarios (efficiency: 59 % for alkaline vs. 41 % for PEM; gas quality: 73 % for alkaline vs. 27 % for PEM). This prevalence may arise from the greater maturity and scalability of alkaline systems, their perceived cost-effectiveness and industrial prioritization, despite PEM being acknowledged as more suitable for flexible operation. On the other hand, durability and degradation aspects receive more extensive attention for PEM technology (18 % for alkaline vs. 82 % for PEM). Regarding this last point, the trend might be associated with more comprehensive studies examining the behavior of PEM membranes in electrolysis conditions.

After bringing attention to the deficiencies from the existing literature, the remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the primary concepts explored in this review, covering the basics of alkaline and PEM electrolysis, defining each key performance indicator and introducing the concept of intermittency as considered in this paper, Section 3 reviews and classifies relevant literature related to the impacts of intermittency at cell, stack and system levels.

2. Overview on low-temperature electrolysis, concept of intermittency and key performance indicators

2.1. Electrochemical background

Electrolysis is an electrochemical reaction driven by the application of electrical potential, which causes water molecules to break down and produce dioxygen and dihydrogen:

An electrolysis process combines two half-reactions called oxygen evolution reaction (OER) and hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) involved in the transfer of electronic and ionic species. In PEM electrolysis, water molecules are split into oxygen, electrons and protons at the anode. Protons and electrons are then transported to the cathode to

recombine and form hydrogen. In alkaline electrolysis, water molecules entering the cathode are reduced into hydrogen molecules and OH^- ions when applying an electrical current, while OH^- ions are oxidized to form oxygen and water molecules at the anode. The overall reaction is described in Fig. 3a and b for respectively PEM and alkaline technology.

Electrolysis requires the presence of an ionic conductor surrounded on both sides by electronic conductors and active layers [15]: i) an electrolyte ensuring ionic conductivity between both electrodes, ii) active surfaces enhancing the kinetic activity of the electrochemical reaction, iii) current collectors enabling the transport of electrons to the active surfaces and iv) bipolar plates supplying the electrodes with reagent and ensuring the evacuation of the product gas. Collectively, these elements converge to specific sites known as triple phase boundaries (TPB) where electronic conductor, ionic conduction and catalyst enable the electrolysis reaction, as illustrated in Fig. 3c.

Electrolysis can be described from both electrochemical and thermodynamic standpoints. In the context of an ideal electrolysis cell operating under constant temperature and pressure conditions, the energy balance is ascribed to the enthalpy change ΔH , described as follows:

$$\Delta H = \Delta G + T\Delta S \quad (2)$$

In Equation (2), the free Gibbs energy ΔG is the minimum amount of electrical energy required for the electrochemical reaction to occur. $T\Delta S$ is the thermal energy needed to trigger the reaction, as the electrolysis is an endothermic process which requires thermal energy in addition to electricity. For low-temperature electrolysis, the reaction endothermicity is offset by the introduction of additional heat brought by irreversibilities.

The Faraday law defines the free Gibbs energy ΔG following Equation (3):

$$\Delta G = nU_{rev}F \quad (3)$$

where $n = 2$ is the number of transferred electrons, F is the Faraday constant, and U_{rev} is the reversible potential defined as the minimal potential for the water splitting reaction to occur, equal to 1.23 V at standard temperature and pressure conditions. The minimum potential to be applied to the cell corresponds to the thermoneutral potential U_{tn} and is defined by:

$$U_{tn} = \Delta H / nF \quad (4)$$

At standard conditions, the thermoneutral potential U_{tn} is equal to 1.48 V. If the applied potential is equal to U_{tn} , the required energy is then totally brought into electrical energy. At a potential higher than U_{tn} , the process then turns exothermic [16]. Fig. 4 depicts the change in ΔH and ΔG with temperature variation.

Fig. 2. a) Breakdown of reviewed publications by operational scale, b) by key performance indicator and technology.

Fig. 3. Schematic views of a) a PEM electrolysis cell, b) an alkaline electrolysis cell, c) TPB. Inspired by Ref. [14] with permission from Elsevier.

Fig. 4. Thermodynamics process involved in water electrolysis [17].

The total cell potential U_{cell} is given by the following expression:

$$U_{cell} = U_{rev} + \eta_{ohm} + \eta_{act} + \eta_{diff} \quad (5)$$

In Equation (5), the ohmic overpotentials η_{ohm} generated by the electrochemical reaction are related to the internal resistivity of the materials constituting the cell components and result from both electronic and ionic flows, the activation overpotentials η_{act} are closely linked to the electrochemical kinetics of the electronic transfer reactions occurring at the interface electrode/electrolyte, and the diffusion overpotentials η_{diff} are related to concentration gradients resulting in slow mass transport. Fig. 5 provides graphical views of the typical voltage

contributions in PEM and alkaline electrolysis.

2.2. Concept of intermittency as considered in this review

Before delving into the core topic of this review, it seems important to provide a precise definition of the concept of intermittency as considered throughout the remainder of this paper. In a broad context, intermittency refers to the fluctuating electrical supply conditions under which the electrolyzer can be subjected during its operation. It can result in i) varying setpoint over time due to the fluctuating events from the incoming electrical power and ii) repetitive changes in the system operating state inducing start-up, shut-down and idle periods. Intermittencies can stem from either a fluctuating energy source or the production demand defined by the consumer downstream. On the one hand, intermittencies can be induced by the variability of meteorological and environmental conditions when the incoming electricity comes from a renewable energy source. In this scenario, the system setpoint is equal to the power received by the electrolyzer. The integration of renewable sources into the operation of electrolyzers therefore requires consideration of different timescales of intermittency. Short-term intermittencies, occurring within seconds to minutes, can be caused by sudden shifts in weather conditions, such as the movement of clouds or variations in wind speed. Medium-term intermittencies, with variations ranging from days to weeks, may result from diurnal cycles and daily weather changes. Finally, long-term intermittencies, spanning from months to years, allow for capturing seasonal fluctuations. On the other hand, load intermittency can be related to the consumer needs. In this scenario, the system setpoint is equal to the consumer production demand. This straightforward description of intermittency turns into a complex issue when applied to electrolyzers which are usually manufactured to operate steadily and in most cases, under nominal conditions, generating impacts across all levels of system operation. Besides, a significant number of case studies when dealing with intermittent operation can emerge from each of the main system configurations

Fig. 5. Typical contributions of cell voltage of a) a PEM cell at temperature and pressure conditions of respectively 80 °C and 1 bar. Simulation results from Ref. [18]. Reprinted with permission from Elsevier. b) an atmospheric alkaline cell polarization at 60 °C. Simulation results from Ref. [9].

presented in Table 1, depending on the parameters conditioning the overall system architecture. In a case where the electrolyzer is connected to the grid, the intermittent operation can arise from a certain number of external parameters, e.g. the grid operating state to provide grid services or the electricity cost when the setpoint is in terms of production demand [19]. In a case where the electrolyzer is off-grid, the nature of the intermittent profile both depends on the system internal parameters e.g. the sizing of the renewable plant and the electrolyzer and the electrical supply conditions, but also on external parameters e.g. the meteorological and environmental conditions to which the system is subjected. For instance, the conversion efficiency of a PV plant depends on its intrinsic features e.g. its design, the material components, and external factors e.g. the incidence angle of the installation, the level of solar irradiation and the outdoor temperature. Similarly, the efficiency of a

wind farm depends on factors such as elevation and the geographic layout of the surrounding landscape. This non-exhaustive list of parameters underscores the complexity of devising a universal definition of intermittency, given that each case study involving intermittent operation entails a distinct combination of these factors.

In short, addressing intermittency issues requires considering the three following features: i) the electrolyzer operates in most cases under dynamic part-load conditions, ii) the electrolyzer undergoes frequent setpoint changes during its operation, iii) the two previous statements involve regular changes in the system operational state. This review aims at addressing the issues arising from all these conditions.

Table 1
Main system architectures involving intermittent operation. Inspired by Ref. [20] with permission of Olivier.

System architecture	Description
<p>The diagram shows a power grid (P_{grid}) connected to a 'load management' block. The load management block is connected to an electrolyzer (I_{H2}^{grid}) and a 'consumer' block. The consumer block is also connected to the electrolyzer. The electrolyzer is controlled by the consumer's H₂ demand.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The electrolyzer is electrically supplied with the grid; • The electrolyzer is subjected to the intermittent consumer H₂ demand and is controlled in terms of H₂ production rate; • The incoming electrical power is a consequence of the consumer H₂ demand and appears as an infinite source.
<p>The diagram shows a power grid (P_{grid}) connected to a 'load management' block. The load management block is connected to an electrolyzer (I_{H2}^{grid}) and a 'consumer' block. The electrolyzer is controlled by the grid's power requirements.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The electrolyzer is electrically supplied with the grid; • The electrolyzer is subjected to grid intermittent power requirements (grid services) and is controlled in terms of power; • The incoming electrical power is constrained by the grid demand.
<p>The diagram shows a renewable energy source (P_{RES}) connected to a 'load management' block. The load management block is connected to an electrolyzer (I_{H2}^{grid}) and a 'consumer' block. The electrolyzer is controlled by the renewable energy source's availability. An 'electricity storage' unit is also connected to the load management block.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The electrolyzer is not connected to the grid and is fully supplied with a renewable energy source. In this configuration, a storage unit can be added in order to release power to the electrolyzer when the renewable energy source is unavailable and to absorb power when the produced electricity exceeds the electrolyzer capacity; • The electrolyzer is subjected to the intermittent nature of the renewable energy source and is controlled in terms of power; • The level of H₂ production is a consequence of the electrical input power; • The incoming electrical power is a constraint of the availability of the renewable energy source.
<p>The diagram shows a power grid (P_{grid}) and a renewable energy source (P_{RES}) connected to a 'load management' block. The load management block is connected to an electrolyzer (I_{H2}^{grid}) and a 'consumer' block. The electrolyzer is controlled by the renewable energy source's availability and is also connected to the grid.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The electrolyzer is connected to the grid and is electrically supplied with a renewable energy source; • When the electrical production exceeds the demand, the surplus production is delivered to the electrolyzer; • The electrolyzer is subjected to the intermittent nature of the renewable energy source and is controlled in terms of power; • The level of H₂ production is a consequence of the electrical input power; • The incoming electrical power is a constraint of the availability of the renewable energy source.

2.3. Key performance indicators

An electrolyzer is a multiphysics and multiscale technology involving the interaction of multiple physical areas, such as fluid and electrical dynamics, electrochemistry, and heat transfer, occurring at various operational scales, ranging from the molecular level of reactions to macroscopic system dynamics. While the cell constitutes the core of the electrolysis process, it alone cannot guarantee the generation of a substantial amount of hydrogen. As a result, the association of multiple individual cells interconnected in series through bipolar plates to form a stack is essential. The proper operation of the stack requires in turn the integration of a large number of auxiliaries whose main functions can be summarized as follows [14]: (i) thermal management of the stack, (ii) flow rate and water/electrolyte concentration regulation at the inlet, (iii) gas purity and overall process safety, (iv) gas evacuation and pressure control, (v) power supply management. Altogether, these additional components constitute the Balance-of-Plant (BoP) of the system. The integration of intermittent operation into electrolyzers and the assessment of the associated impacts on system performance therefore requires i) considering all system operational scales and ii) taking into account the multi-physical interactions associated to the system dynamics. Considering the performance indicators themselves, intermittent operation can have significant impacts on the efficiency, the level of gas quality and the durability of electrolyzers. For this reason, the review proposes to specifically focus on these three performance indicators.

First, gas quality pertains to the reality that the hydrogen leaving the stack is never totally pure, and necessarily contains a certain amount of foreign and undesirable bodies, mostly driven by crossover mechanisms occurring during the electrolysis process. It is usually assessed at the cell or stack level, by measuring the presence rate of oxygen and water residues in the produced hydrogen. At the system level, purification units and dryers are integrated to the BoP to both remove oxygen and water residues and therefore to ensure a high quality of the hydrogen end-product at the system outlet.

Second, the accurate definition of efficiency and the approaches employed to evaluate it are not standardized in the existing literature. It is therefore worthwhile to revisit the main ones. Efficiency at the cell or stack level can theoretically be assessed according to the Faraday law, which reflects the fact that the produced hydrogen is directly proportional to the input current [20]. However, in practical scenarios, not all the electrons passing through the cell contribute to the reaction, primarily due to losses associated with shunt currents encountered in alkaline electrolysis and parasitic reactions in both alkaline and PEM electrolysis. To take into account these losses, the Faradaic efficiency η_F defined as the ratio between the actual amount of produced hydrogen and the theoretical amount of hydrogen that would be generated under ideal conditions, can be introduced:

$$\eta_F (\%) = \dot{n}_{H_2, cell} / (I / 2F) \quad (6)$$

where $\dot{n}_{H_2, cell}$ (mol/s) is the actual H_2 production flow rate at the cell output and I (A) is the current entering the cell.

Additionally, the use of polarization curves is a traditional practice to describe the electrical performance of an electrolysis cell or a stack [21]. These curves depict the kinetics of the electrolysis process under galvanostatic conditions, maintaining a constant current density and specific operating conditions. The polarization curve is a valuable tool in comprehending how current variation affect the cell voltage.

An alternative method widely used in the industry to assess efficiency is based on hydrogen production [20]. When an ideal DC current is applied, the cell efficiency can be assessed by comparing the energy content of the produced hydrogen with the energy consumed during the electrolysis process, introducing the voltage efficiency η_V and giving rise to the following equation:

$$\eta_{cell} (\%) = (\dot{n}_{H_2, cell} * \Delta H) / (U_{cell} * I) = \eta_F * (U_m / U_{cell}) = \eta_F * \eta_V \quad (7)$$

The expression at the stack level can be easily deduced by including the number of cells constituting the stack. However, as mentioned earlier, assessing the efficiency at the system level requires integrating the BoP, which introduces additional energy consumption. The system efficiency can be expressed as the ratio between the total equivalent power contained in the end-product hydrogen and the electrical power input, as follows [13,20]:

$$\eta_{sys} (\%LHV_{H_2} \text{ or } \%HHV_{H_2}) = ((LHV_{H_2} \text{ or } HHV_{H_2}) * \dot{m}_{H_2}) / P_{sys} \quad (8)$$

where the low heating value $LHV_{H_2} = 33.33 \text{ kWh} \cdot \text{kg}_{H_2}^{-1}$ represents the energy content of hydrogen when considering the heat released during combustion without accounting for the heat required to vaporize water, and the high heating value $HHV_{H_2} = 39.5 \text{ kWh} \cdot \text{kg}_{H_2}^{-1}$ includes the heat from vaporizing water. P_{sys} includes both the stack and BoP consumptions and \dot{m}_{H_2} is the difference between the total hydrogen production rate of cells at the stack outlet, obtained from Equation (7), and the hydrogen losses induced by crossover mechanisms and other losses occurring in the system.

The specific consumption is an additional valuable performance metric defined as the quantity of electricity required to produce a standardized amount of hydrogen. When considering the overall system, it then accounts for both the stack and BoP power consumptions and can be defined as follows [13]:

$$\varepsilon_{sys} (\text{kWh} \cdot \text{kg}_{H_2}^{-1}) = \int P_{sys} dt / \int \dot{m}_{H_2} dt \quad (9)$$

Finally, a key indicator to consider when analyzing the long-term performance of an electrolyzer is its durability. It can be assessed by measuring the degradation rate of the system, i.e. the time the system takes to experience performance loss. A method for evaluating the degradation rate \dot{U}_N involves measuring the rate of voltage increase over N time periods, based on the following equation (10):

$$\dot{U}_N (\text{mV} \cdot 1000\text{h}^{-1}) = \sum_i^N U(t_{i+1}) - U(t_i) / \sum_i^N \Delta t_i \quad (10)$$

Additionally, incorporating supplementary indicators derived from in-situ electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) methods presents an avenue for refining the interpretation of polarization curves. These indicators offer crucial insights into the individual contributions of electrochemical and transport losses during cell polarization. Specifically, the examination of Nyquist or Bode diagrams facilitates the clear identification of two principal sources of performance degradation: the low frequency resistance (LFR), associated with protonic and electronic conduction within the membrane-electrode assembly (MEA), and the high frequency resistance (HFR), encapsulating electrode kinetics and reactant gas mass transport [22]. Beyond these foundational insights, additional electrochemical parameters, including double layer effects and charge transfer resistance, can be elucidated through complex non-linear least square (CNLS) analysis employing appropriate equivalent electrical circuit (EEC) models [23].

Table 2 provides an overview of the various indicators introduced earlier at all levels of the system operation, along with the commonly used expressions to assess them.

3. Review on the impacts of intermittency on alkaline and PEM electrolyzers

3.1. Efficiency

The literature suggests that the stack efficiency theoretically rises as far as the electrical load decreases. However, as mentioned earlier, assessing the efficiency of an electrolyzer at the system level requires

Table 2
Overview on the performance indicators examined in this paper.

Scale	Performance	Indicator	Expression	Unit
Cell	Efficiency	Polarization curve	–	–
Cell, stack	Efficiency	Faradaic efficiency	$\dot{n}_{H_2,cell} = (\eta_F \cdot I) / 2F$	%
Cell, stack, system	Efficiency	Energy efficiency	$\eta_{LHV/HHV} = ((LHV_{H_2} \text{ or } HHV_{H_2}) \cdot \dot{m}_{H_2})$	%LHV, %HHV
Cell	Efficiency	Voltage efficiency	$\eta_V = U_{in} / U_{cell}$	%
Cell	Efficiency	Energy efficiency	$\eta_{cell} = \eta_F \cdot \eta_V$	%
Stack, system	Efficiency	Specific consumption	$\epsilon_{sys} = \int P_{sys} dt / \int \dot{m}_{H_2} dt$	kWh·kg ⁻¹ H ₂
Cell, stack, system	Gas quality	HTO, OTH	–	%
Cell, stack	Durability	Rate of voltage increase	$\dot{U}_N = \sum_i^N U(t_{i+1}) - U(t_i) / \sum_i^N \Delta t_i$	mV·1000h ⁻¹ , μV·h ⁻¹
Cell, stack	Durability	LFR, HFR	–	Ω, Ω·cm ⁻²

integrating the BoP and the system control loops beyond the stack, which gives rise to additional issues related to i) the introduction of additional energy consumers, ii) various types of hydrogen losses across the system, iii) electrical losses encountered in power converter units and iv) the change in system operational state over its operation. Notably, the introduction of these additional issues is apparent in the efficiency curve, highlighting a noticeable difference in trends between the two operational scales. The introduction of the BoP induces a higher overall specific energy consumption compared to the stack level, as depicted in Fig. 7. Moreover, the stack-level specific consumption rises with increasing load, whereas the opposite trend is expected at the system level. However, as efficiency is a techno-dependent indicator, operational profiles need to be applied to reinforce these assertions. This section aims at reviewing the main efficiency issues arising from the cell and stack level to the full system level. Furthermore, it underscores the significant lack of quantitative assessments based on real intermittent profiles at the system level, encompassing both alkaline and PEM technologies.

Table 3 provides a condensed overview of publications classified by broad research topic for each technology and scale.

3.1.1. Issues related to crossover mechanisms

Within an electrolysis cell, achieving perfect gas tightness is

Table 3
Identified publications addressing efficiency issues.

Technology	Scale	Research topics	References
Alkaline	Cell/stack	Evaluation of the impacts of operating conditions on efficiency.	[16,24–31]
Alkaline	System	Evaluation of the impacts of operating conditions on efficiency.	[32,33]
Alkaline	Cell/stack	Application of real intermittent power profiles.	[34–52]
Alkaline	System	Application of real intermittent power profiles.	[53–62]
Alkaline	System	Performance characterization during transient steps.	[63,64]
Alkaline	Cell/stack	Effect of dynamic design/process conditions on efficiency.	[65–71]
Alkaline	Cell/stack	Effect of power conversion on efficiency.	[72–76]
Alkaline	System	Effect of dynamic design/process conditions on efficiency.	[77]
PEM	Cell/stack	Evaluation of the impacts of operating conditions on efficiency.	[78–92]
PEM	System	Evaluation of the impacts of operating conditions on efficiency.	[93,94]
PEM	Cell/stack	Application of real intermittent power profiles.	[95–110]
PEM	System	Application of real intermittent power profiles.	[20,57, 111–115]
PEM	Cell/stack	Performance characterization during transient steps.	[91, 116–119]
PEM	Cell/stack	Effect of power conversion on efficiency.	[120,121]
PEM	Cell/stack	Effect of dynamic design/process conditions on efficiency.	[87]

challenging, as hydrogen can diffuse towards the anode while oxygen can diffuse towards the cathode by convective and diffusive transfer mechanisms due to gas solubility and mobility through the materials constituting the MEA [14,17,79,122–124]. On the one hand, convective gas transport is attributed to the movement of ions when an electric field is applied. It occurs: i) by electroosmosis drag as long as an electrical setpoint is applied to the cells, ii) when there is a pressure difference between the anodic and cathodic compartments. Working at high pressures reduces the need of integrating additional compressors downstream, which holds some benefits considering the entire system process. However, differential pressure promotes so-called crossover phenomena and generates additional issues at the stack level. On the other hand, diffusive gas transport is attributed to local hydrogen supersaturated concentrations occurring at membrane/electrode interfaces. De Groot et al. [69] recognized this transport mechanism as the primary cause of crossover phenomena in alkaline electrolysis. In short, crossover mechanisms, depicted in Fig. 6, depend on the electrical setpoint, the operating temperature and pressure conditions, and the

Fig. 6. Crossover mechanisms in a PEM electrolysis cell [123]. In this illustration, A: H⁺ protons transport through the electrolyte; B: gas crossover driven by water electroosmosis drag; C: gas diffusion promoted by concentration gradients; D: H₂ permeation promoted by anodic and cathodic pressure differential; E: gas recombination in water. Reprinted with permission from Elsevier.

Fig. 7. Simulation results depicting the specific consumption of a PEM electrolyzer at different setpoints and temperatures. Reprinted with permission from Olivier [20].

geometrical and physico-chemical properties as the porosity of the membrane, tortuosity, and the hydrogen solubility of the components constituting the electrolysis cell. Both alkaline and PEM technologies face crossover issues, although it is found more critical in alkaline electrolysis as gas can dissolve in the liquid electrolyte. Besides, the two main mechanisms promoting gas crossover in alkaline electrolysis have been identified as being i) the gas diffusion through the diaphragm and ii) the gas dissolution in the alkaline KOH electrolyte [125]. Crossover mechanisms promote the generation of parasitic reactions, where gases that are meant to be separated can recombine to form water or react with each other. This results in the formation of byproducts, which consume energy without contributing to the reaction. Furthermore, uncontrolled crossover leads to mixed gases, reducing the Faradaic efficiency of the electrolysis reaction. As discussed in Section 2.3, Faradaic efficiency measures the ratio of the actual electrolysis reaction to the total current passed through the system. When gases cross over, this ratio diminishes, impacting the overall efficiency. Interestingly, the permeation rate is not heavily influenced by the electrical setpoint and remains more or less constant over the entire operating range of the cell. Thus, the amount of transferred gas is proportionally higher at low load ranges as far as the hydrogen flow rate decreases. During intermittent operation, an electrolyzer typically runs below its nominal capacity. The amplification of crossover phenomena at lower loads suggests that intermittent operation theoretically results in a higher permeation rate compared to steady operation under nominal conditions. This, in turn, has an impact on its efficiency. Although this paper does not extensively address safety issues, it is worth noting that gas crossover also poses major risks in the formation of an explosive atmosphere (ATEX), with the lower explosive limit (LEL) of hydrogen in oxygen being 4 % at 20 °C. Operating at low power ranges can lead to a risky increase of the hydrogen content in oxygen due to crossover mechanisms, in addition to impacting the quality of the product gas, efficiency and durability [10]. For this reason, manufacturers establish a threshold limit for part-load operation to guarantee that the electrolyzer remains within a safe operational range. This limit varies from one manufacturer to another and differs according to the technology specifications. For the case of alkaline electrolyzers, the threshold limit is usually set around 20 % of their nominal capacity, while it typically ranges from 5 % to 10 % for PEM electrolyzers [10]. For this reason as well, the literature often suggests that PEM technology is more flexible and compatible with intermittent energy sources compared to alkaline technology. Considering the operational flexibility of electrolyzers becomes crucial when discussing intermittency. This is particularly significant because the operational points of a PV or wind load profile may potentially drop below the electrolyzer minimum operating limit, depending on the variability of meteorological conditions.

3.1.2. Issues related to stack irreversibilities

Within an electrolysis stack, the cells do not behave uniformly. Thus,

assessing performance at the stack level involves operating in a less controlled environment due to the fact that the assembly of cells introduces additional contact resistances. The stack efficiency therefore results lower than the average efficiency of single cells. However, in this review, it has been chosen to address collectively the reported issues at both cell and stack levels. At the cell and stack levels, efficiency is significantly dependent on the system operating conditions, with some variables having a more pronounced impact. Specifically, the variables exerting the greatest influence include electrical setpoint, stack temperature, and crossover mechanisms. At the cell and stack levels, efficiency can be described in terms of Faradaic efficiency or energy efficiency. Both metrics are heavily influenced by the operating pressure, temperature and the electrical setpoint, but behave differently.

First, the Faradaic efficiency represents the utilization rate of electrons involved in the hydrogen production process. It is affected by both current leakage and gas crossover. At lower power ranges, parasitic reactions become more prominent than the actual electrolysis reaction, thereby promoting heat generation and chemical recombination of products into by-products. Consequently, Faradaic losses limit hydrogen production, leading to a decline in Faradaic efficiency. On the other hand, Faradaic efficiency tends to increase at lower pressure and temperature, as crossover phenomena are mitigated under such conditions. According to Ref. [82], it is primarily affected by pressure increase and membrane thinning, in the case of PEM electrolysis.

Second, the energy efficiency of an electrolysis stack accounts for both the utilization of electrons involved in the reaction and the level of irreversibilities conditioned by the current/voltage conditions to which the stack is subjected. It is well documented that operating at high temperatures limits the generation of irreversibilities, conferring to the electrolyte a better conductivity and increasing the reaction activity, which has a positive effect on efficiency. This last statement can be illustrated with the Arrhenius equation (11), showing that increasing temperature enhances the probability of molecules collisions, and therefore the kinetic rate of the reaction. Consequently, at higher temperatures, the stack requires less energy to overcome the activation barrier and limits the heat losses.

$$k = Ae^{E_a/RT} \quad (11)$$

where k is the kinetic rate, A the Arrhenius factor and E_a the activation energy.

Operating intermittently therefore induces additional issues related to the temperature variation, as lowering temperature decreases the electrolyte conductivity during periods when the load is low or zero [126].

However, there is no real consensus regarding the effect of pressure on the efficiency at the stack level. From a thermodynamic viewpoint, the literature often associates pressure increase with better kinetic reactions, i.e. better efficiency, due to the reduction in the size of formed bubbles which act as a barrier to the catalytic sites [12]. Conversely, experimental tests conducted by Ursua et al. [34] depicted a decline in efficiency with pressure increase. This result was attributed to an enhancement of crossover phenomena and hydrogen losses at the alkaline stack inlet.

Meanwhile, energy efficiency seems to be more affected by the electrical setpoint rather than the operating conditions. Specifically, it is well established that load increase enhances the irreversible processes, which is naturally accompanied with an efficiency drop. In practical terms, intermittent operation implies that the stack dynamically operates most of the time below the nominal setpoint, which would result in average in higher specific consumption during intermittent operation. The results provided by Ursua et al. [34] corroborate these statements, with an efficiency of 74.7 %HHV and a specific consumption of 4.741 kWh·Nm⁻³H₂ under nominal operation and an efficiency of 77.7 %HHV and a specific consumption of 4.557 kWh·Nm⁻³H₂ under wind conditions.

Besides considering the fact that intermittent operation implies that the stack dynamically operates in part-load conditions, intermittency also involves multiple ramp-up and ramp-down events during the operation, requiring careful consideration. In their study, Lee et al. [109] conducted intermittent tests on a PEM cell assembly to assess the impacts of intermittent current mimicking wind conditions and dynamic ramps on the behavior of mass transport within the porous transport layers (PTL). Results showed that i) the increase in gas accumulation was more pronounced during intermittent operation and was accompanied with an overpotential increase of 6 %, and ii) the direction and the stiffness of ramp-up and ramp-down events both impact the behavior of mass transport. Specifically, it was observed that stiff ramp-up and ramp-down events worsen the level of gas saturation, which is a good indicator of performance loss. Indeed, gas saturation occurs when the production rate of gases exceeds their rate of diffusion or removal, leading to a gas accumulation within the cells. This specific condition can impact mass transfer mechanisms and induce local regions of high resistances within the cells, thereby reducing the overall stack efficiency. Furthermore, acting as a barrier to water flow to the membrane, the latter can dry out, affecting its ionic conductivity and thereby causing an increase in ohmic overpotentials and reducing the overall cell durability.

3.1.3. Issues related to the integration of the balance-of-plant and other subsystems

Moving from the stack to the system level entails considering additional energy consumption induced by the BoP and the integration of additional subsystems downstream the electrolyzer. Stansberry et al. [111] identified four main factors contributing to the specific energy consumption at the system level: the stack consumption, the hydrogen lost through the purification process, the system pressurization and gas crossover, and the electrical consumption of electrical units and of the BoP. Notably, the electrical consumption of auxiliary components i.e. the circulation pumps, fans, control systems, and purification units represents the most significant part of the system consumption at low power ranges, leading to an overall decrease of the system efficiency during intermittent operation. This is attributed to the fact that auxiliaries consume a constant power across the entire operating range of the electrolyzer, resulting in a proportionally higher consumption when the system operates at low loads. The highest efficiency of 59.88 % HHV was achieved at full load capacity, compared to 43.96 % HHV under wind-type conditions. In Ref. [20], Olivier developed a multiphysics model using the Bond Graph (BG) formalism to quantify the phenomena affecting a PEM electrolyzer, incorporating the impacts of various types of intermittent operation at different time scales, ranging from seconds to seasonal periods. Short-term simulations were conducted to analyze the system dynamics and identify intermittent operation-related issues. Modelling results revealed that the electrolyzer consumed 7.11 kWh·Nm⁻³ during nominal operation, compared to 7.51 kWh·Nm⁻³ during a PV-type operation. The main impacts on efficiency were attributed to the system thermal, fluidic, and electrical dynamics. Crespi et al. [115] assessed the ability of a 60 kW PEM electrolyzer to withstand dynamic part-load operation. Similarly, the authors observed a decline in performance when the system operates below its nominal capacity, with a specific consumption of approximately 67 kWh·kg⁻¹H₂ at maximum load, compared to 80 kWh·kg⁻¹H₂ at 60 % part-load conditions and 140 kWh·kg⁻¹H₂ at 30 % part-load conditions. Once again, performance losses were mainly attributed to the energy consumption of the BoP components, where 80 % were associated to the recirculation pump. Pressure variation is also to be mentioned when discussing intermittent operation as it impacts system performance. This stems from the necessity to prevent undue increase or decrease in pressure within the electrolyzer as the flow rate experiences upward or downward shifts. In these conditions, the gas produced must be immediately absorbed by the downstream components. However, achieving instantaneous absorption is inherently unattainable, resulting in pressure

fluctuations within the system. Although efforts can be made to mitigate this effect through the utilization of pressure regulators, the variability of flow rates inevitably leads to pressure fluctuations. The extent of this fluctuation depends on the specific hydrogen storage technology or application downstream. In certain cases, additional equipment, such as a buffer volume, might be added to effectively manage these pressure variations. However, the introduction of such equipment may contribute to a heightened level of complexity in the system operation, threatens the overall system performance and generates additional costs.

3.1.4. Issues related to power conversion

When an electrolyzer operates under intermittent operation, power converters have to constantly adapt to the dynamic setpoint, which generate ripple effects more or less significant depending on the converter ripple factor. These unwanted phenomena, in turn, impact the quality of the power conversion and electrolyzer supply conditions, and consequently the overall system performance. Buitendach et al. [121] carried out an investigation on a laboratory-scale PEM electrolyzer. Results depicted a decrease in the energy consumption when the ripple frequency increased. However, no specific waveform effects were identified in this study. Additionally, it was observed that only power consumption was affected, whereas none of frequency or waveform influenced the hydrogen flow rate. In addition, Koponen et al. [120] found that transistor power converters lowers the specific energy consumption of the tested PEM electrolyzer to 14 % compared to thyristor power converters. This last outcome has been supported for alkaline technology as well [72].

3.1.5. Issues related to thermal dynamics

Conventional electrolyzers are carefully designed to maintain the stack temperature at optimal conditions. In the case of low-temperature electrolyzers, as long as the current is positive, the stack operates under exothermic conditions and releases heat due to irreversibilities, i.e. the cell voltage is higher than the thermoneutral voltage in these conditions. The amount of heat produced by the stack is directly proportional to the input current involved in the reaction. Consequently, higher currents lead to a higher amount of heat generation. In low-temperature electrolyzers, the stacks are heated up thanks to their internal irreversibilities, and the stack temperature is regulated to avoid exceeding the nominal temperature and prevent excessively high degradation rates. Consequently, the stack temperature is directly influenced by the load conditions and may require a certain time to reach its nominal temperature [20]. Operating the stack at a temperature lower than its nominal level results in significant losses in system efficiency. When supplied with intermittent power conditions, the electrolyzer struggles to maintain its nominal temperature due to frequent start-up, shut-down periods and fluctuations coming from the electrical load profile. Besides, it is important to note that the thermal response to the same intermittent electrical load profile is specific to each technology considered in this paper, as the thermal capacity of an alkaline electrolyzer differs from that of a PEM electrolyzer. However, at the system level, the outlet temperature remains relatively stable. The purification of hydrogen involves the integration of cooling systems that bring the outlet temperature to approximately the ambient temperature, regardless of the technology considered [15]. Results presented in Fig. 7 indicate that the system specific consumption is significantly influenced by both its electrical setpoint and temperature [20]. Besides, it should be mentioned that an efficiency curve is specific to each electrolyzer and does not exhibit a general trend. In many commercial electrolyzers, the minimum specific consumption is typically observed within the load range of 40 %–60 %.

3.1.6. Issues related to hydrogen losses

Beyond the thermal aspect, efficiency decrease is also attributed to hydrogen losses, arising from unwanted mechanisms occurring at the stack level, e.g. crossover phenomena, shunt current in the case of

alkaline technology etc., but also from regeneration processes during the operation of the purification units and hydrogen venting and leaks at the system level. The study from Ref. [111] shows that the gas dryer operation accounts for 90 % of the total hydrogen losses at system level. Results from Stansberry et al. [111] illustrated that hydrogen losses were most significant at low power ranges and constituted the primary source of energy consumption when electrical supply conditions exceed 30 %. In PEM electrolyzers, opting for a thicker membrane is desirable to reduce crossover phenomena and mitigate associated issues related to recombination reactions which in turn limit hydrogen losses. However, designing this parameter involves a trade-off. Increasing the membrane thickness simultaneously leads to an increase in ohmic overpotentials, resulting in lower process efficiency [20].

In the case of PEM electrolyzers, an additional issue related to filling and draining phenomena arises when the system operates intermittently [20]. Transport mechanisms of water from the oxygen to the hydrogen side through the polymer membrane rises the water level in the hydrogen separator. To counterbalance these phenomena, drainages are scheduled during the system operation when the water level in the hydrogen separator exceeds the tolerated threshold. However, these draining phenomena lead to pressure drops and consequently, variation of the hydrogen flow at the system outlet. Intermittent operation implying setpoint variation then becomes an issue, compared to a steady-state operation, as the frequency of flow drops increases with the setpoint.

3.1.7. Issues related to system operational state transitions

Long-term operation under fluctuating electrical conditions and dynamic events characterized by steep setpoint ramps up and down involving regular start-ups and shut-downs are unavoidable when the electrolyzer is supplied with an intermittent electrical source. Thus, addressing issues stemming from the repetitive changes in the system operational states is crucial as they affect not only the short-term system performance indicators including efficiency and gas purity, but also its long-term performance. This last point will be further discussed in Section 3.3. During a cold start-up, the auxiliaries are switched on and the electrolyzer is driven through safety measures and several time-consuming steps including a pressurization stage, the activation of purification units and system heating, inducing additional power consumption and hydrogen losses. The shut-down process involves the system depressurization and various safety measures related to crossover-related issues, which have to be launched quickly. An electrolyzer operating at high pressure will therefore take a longer time to reach a totally inert state than one operating at atmospheric pressure. Yet, it is necessary to ensure that the power supply needed for the quick launch of these operational steps is sufficient to ensure the system safety, which an intermittent energy source is not able to guarantee. Moreover, intermittent operation may lead to situations where the electrical setpoint drops below the minimum threshold. In this situation, the system automatically leaves the production state to initiate a shut-down. Pressurization hydrogen is then lost through the venting lines and additional energy required to complete each step of system shut-down is consumed. To minimize the energy consumption associated with frequent start-ups and shut-downs, most electrolyzers incorporate stand-by periods. These phases maintain pressure and keep the electrolyzer close to its nominal operating temperature, facilitating quicker system resumption from a hot state compared to cold start-ups [20]. Nevertheless, the continuous operation of auxiliaries during stand-by increases energy consumption without producing hydrogen. Furthermore, due to pressure maintaining, gas crossover still occurs during stand-by periods leading to decreased gas purity and greater demand on purification units, resulting in higher electricity consumption. Additionally, despite maintaining proximity to the required level, temperature may slightly drop below its nominal range, affecting efficiency. The intermittent nature of the operation therefore poses a challenge because frequent transitions between different operational states during system operation lead to reduced

performance.

3.2. Gas quality

Crossover mechanisms can compromise the purity level of hydrogen production. When gases cross over from one electrode to another, undesired reactions can occur, leading to impurities in the final hydrogen product. Minimizing crossover is therefore crucial for maintaining high hydrogen purity in electrolysis processes. In current electrolyzers, manufacturers incorporate purification and dryer units at separator outlet to maintain the final hydrogen purity at the required level. Nevertheless, there is no guarantee that the purity level is reached when the system operates under intermittent conditions.

This section brings attention to the significant lack of quantitative studies based on intermittent electrical power profiles and the absence of studies conducted at the system level. Table 4 provides a summary of publications found for each technology based on the broad research topic.

Ursua et al. [34] conducted experimental investigations on a commercial $1 \text{ Nm}^3\text{h}^{-1}$ alkaline electrolyzer under steady-state conditions, exploring the effects of varying current density, operating temperature and pressure on its performance. The obtained results confirmed several main outcomes. First, it was found that the gas purity was significantly affected by high operating temperatures and pressures. For instance, the amount of hydrogen transferred to oxygen (HTO) increased to 0.27 % at a temperature of 65 °C, compared to 0.15 % at 35 °C, while maintaining a nominal current of 120 A. Moreover, the amount of HTO was 4.5 times higher when the stack operated at 25 bar rather than 5 bar. This behavior was attributed to i) an increased gas bubble diffusion rate through the porous diaphragm, facilitated by temperature increase, and ii) a decrease in gas bubble volume with pressure increase, promoting their diffusion through the diaphragm. Same outcomes were found for PEM electrolysis where Omrani et al. [135] attributed the increase of hydrogen crossover to respectively i) an increase of the hydrogen solubility and diffusion coefficient with temperature increase and ii) the reduction of mass transfer coefficient with pressure increase leading to hydrogen supersaturation. Second, the amount of both oxygen transferred to hydrogen (OTH) and HTO showed a strong increase with current decrease. Current decrease leads to a lower production flow rate, causing gas bubbles to take more time to form and exit the cell. Being trapped in the cell for longer, they also increase their diffusion rate across the membrane. Additionally, it is worth noting that, on average, HTO was 10–30 times larger than OTH. This disparity is attributed to the lighter and smaller properties of hydrogen, enhancing its diffusivity through the electrolyte and diaphragm compared to oxygen. Intermittent operation induces fluctuations in operating conditions and frequent changes in the setpoint varying over the system operating range. The increase in gas transfer with decreasing load implies that crossover phenomena are likely to be worsened during intermittent operation compared to steady nominal operation. Experimental results from Ursua et al. [34] have confirmed this statement, indicating that gas transfers during nominal operation were on average 50 % lower than those

Table 4
Identified publications addressing gas quality issues.

Technology	Research topics	References
Alkaline	Effect of operating conditions on gas quality.	[24,32,34]
Alkaline	Effect of intermittent power conditions on gas quality.	[34–36,39,40,48,53,54,61,127,128]
Alkaline	Effect of dynamic design/process conditions on gas quality.	[77,128–131]
PEM	Effect of operating conditions on gas quality.	[80,132]
PEM	Effect of intermittent power conditions on gas quality.	[20,133,134]

observed under dynamic regimes driven by PV and wind sources, which aligns well with the previous observations. Furthermore, it was observed that the intermittent profile exhibiting the highest gas transfers was also the one most affected by power fluctuations. Fig. 8 illustrates the experimental results of hydrogen flow rate, HTO, and OTH over time during PV-type operation of the electrolyzer. Specifically, during high current peaks, crossover was reduced, while the opposite trend was observed at low current ranges.

In addition to the aforementioned findings, Dutton et al. [61] conducted a study on a 10 kW alkaline electrolyzer under simulated wind conditions to examine the effect of load fluctuations at different time scales on gas purity. The experimental results suggested that the level of gas impurity was correlated to the frequency of the fluctuating events. Short-time scale intermittent events ranging from 1 s to 10 s were found to have a more significant impact on gas purity compared to medium-time scale fluctuations ranging from 60 s to 150 s. Similarly, Kiaee et al. [48] conducted experimental tests on an alkaline plant in a refueling station in Norway when supplied with wind power. They observed higher impurities during periods of high fluctuating load, which aligns well with the previous findings. Beyond the operation of the electrolyzer itself, Speckmann et al. [131] investigated the influence of power conversion process on the quality of the gas produced by a lab-scale alkaline electrolysis, and demonstrated that a high current ripple factor in the power converter considerably increases the presence of oxygen impurities in the produced hydrogen.

3.3. Durability and degradation

Intermittent operation involves fluctuations in the electrical load profile, with variations in current density, voltage, and operating conditions (temperature, pressure, flow rate ...), idle, start and stop cycling periods. These dynamic operational features generate thermal and mechanical stresses, including shocks and vibrations, affecting the electrochemical performance and long-term mechanical stability of the system [136]. Most studies have suggested that intermittency negatively impacts durability by worsening chemical, thermo-chemical, physico-chemical and mechanical degradation mechanisms occurring during the cell operation. Meanwhile, some authors have investigated the effect of specific dynamic conditions and have shown that intermittency may have in some cases positive effects on performance. Until now, the majority of studies in the existing literature are based on current or voltage cycling, revealing a notable gap in investigations based on operational intermittent profiles. Harmonized testing protocols defining a framework for test conditions and measurement sequences to assess the short-term performance of low-temperature electrolyzers under

steady-state and dynamic conditions have been proposed in the annual reports of the Joint Research Center (JRC) [13]. Additionally, endeavors to enhance the realistic evaluation of degradation have led to the formulation of specific test protocols. For instance, Spöri et al. [137] introduced an accelerated stress test (AST) designed to emulate commercial lifetimes within shorter test durations. Their findings highlighted the effectiveness of the developed test protocol in swiftly and consistently evaluating the anode catalyst stability. Kozlova et al. [138] implemented two experimental methods for assessing the degradation of PEM MEAs: an AST consisting of dynamic voltage cycling and continuous testing at elevated voltage for 500 h. Overall, a higher degradation rate was found during the constant operation but results also underscored the necessity of using both methods in tandem, as the AST alone offered restricted insights into MEA degradation mechanisms. This feedback highlights the ongoing need for enhancements in current testing methodologies and emphasizes the importance of standardization endeavors aimed at assessing electrolyzer degradation during intermittent operation [11,139]. Evaluating the durability of an electrolysis cell during intermittent conditions appears all the more challenging as it would require appropriate in-situ measurements to capture the ramping effects of intermittency, whereas most reported studies are currently based on ex-situ methods. This step represents a key milestone for the widespread industrialization of current electrolyzers, thereby facilitating the integration of intermittent energies into their operation. In this section, attention is also drawn to the lack of consistency in the reported literature outcomes and the limited number of studies focusing on alkaline technology. Table 5 provides a summary of publications based on broad research topics for each technology.

Most studies concur that intermittent operation leads to a higher decay rate compared to nominal operation. Among them, Rakousky et al. [142] conducted an investigation on the performance decay of a PEM electrolysis cell when operating constantly and undergoing different dynamic cycles. Test conditions are detailed in Table 6. Results revealed a significant performance decay with increasing number of short-time scale fluctuations, which suggests that the impact on durability is closely linked to the frequency of intermittent events during the cell operation. Notably, observations on dynamic modes D and E show that the voltage increase is considerably smaller for the cell operating under longer current cycles (6 h for mode D vs. 10 min for mode E). Furthermore, the higher degree of performance degradation was attributed to the cells operating under constant higher current densities, which tend to experience increased ohmic losses at the Ti-PTL. Besides, the increase in ohmic losses was found to be limited when the current was periodically reduced.

In line with the findings of Rakousky et al., Kuhnert et al. [156] conducted an experimental study to compare the degradation rate of a single PEM cell under two accelerated dynamic PV setups, simulating a year-long operation. The first setup represents a situation where the PEM cell is fully supplied with the PV system, thus incorporating starts and stops in its operation (“PV-AST”) while the second integrates a battery to bypass these specific steps, maintaining a minimum current

Fig. 8. Trend of hydrogen flow rate, HTO, and OTH of the alkaline stack during a PV-type operation [18]. Reprinted with permission from Elsevier.

Table 5
Identified publications addressing durability and degradation issues.

Technology	Research topics	References
PEM	Effect of dynamic electrical conditions and operating conditions on performance degradation.	[138,140–159]
PEM	Effect of design/process conditions and dynamic power cycling on performance degradation.	[149,151,160,161, 161,162]
Alkaline	Effect of dynamic electrical conditions and operating conditions on performance degradation.	[63,163,164]
Alkaline	Effect of design/process conditions and dynamic power cycling on performance degradation.	[165]

Table 6

Experimental conditions for the five tests conducted in [142].

Name	Operation	Value	Operation time
A	Constant	1 A cm ⁻²	1000 h
B	Constant	2 A cm ⁻²	1000 h
C	Dynamic	2 and 1 A cm ⁻² for 6 h each	1000 h
D	Dynamic	2 and 0 A cm ⁻² for 6 h each	1000 h
E	Dynamic	2 and 0 A cm ⁻² for 10 min each	1000 h

density of 1 A cm⁻² (“PV-B-AST”). Results revealed that the irreversible degradation rate under the first PV-AST configuration was almost four times higher (11 mV h⁻¹) than the PV-B-AST configuration (3 mV h⁻¹). Cai et al. [149] carried out a lab-scale study on a PEM MEA and showed that the tested module exhibited a higher decay rate under PV fluctuating conditions (3.5 mV h⁻¹) compared to constant conditions (2.05 mV h⁻¹). Voronova et al. [158] proposed a simulated AST replicating PEM behavior under PV conditions. Findings indicated an accelerated degradation of the cathode electrocatalyst (Pt/C) between voltage ranges of 1.4–1.9 V, possibly attributed to carbon support corrosion and Pt dissolution. Conversely, within voltage ranges of 1.7–1.9 V, an increase in transport overvoltage was observed, associated with the breakdown of CL/membrane and/or CL/PTL interfaces due to altered oxygen bubble growth patterns induced by frequent voltage fluctuations. Additionally, Su et al. [159] conducted a series of three ASTs comprising continuous, square-wave, and PV operation. Findings showed the highest degradation rate during PV operation, measured at 87.7 μV h⁻¹, compared to 22 μV h⁻¹ and 50 μV h⁻¹ at current densities of 1 A cm⁻² and 3 A cm⁻², respectively.

Same outcomes were found for alkaline electrolysis. Bergen et al. [64] experimentally analyzed the behavior of a regenerative residential-scale alkaline electrolyzer subjected to various transient events involving on/off cycles switching and short-time scale events. Results showed a decline in hydrogen production at the stack outlet for any tested dynamic configuration compared to steady-state operation. This production drop was attributed to the progressive formation of a barrier to active sites caused by the accumulation and coalescence of gas bubbles on the upper part of the electrodes, resulting in increased kinetic resistance. This outcome is consistent with the simulated results found in the model of Amores et al. [51]. In addition, local hot spots can be formed at the membrane and catalytic sites when gas bubbles are not homogeneously distributed, which induces thermal stress to the mechanical structure. Besides, it can be mentioned that dynamic operation also enhances the detachment diameter of gas bubbles, i.e. the size reduction of the active area, which inadvertently accompanies the detachment of catalytic sites and impacts the cell durability. Revisiting the study of Bergen et al. [64], results also suggested that short-time

scale events were particularly detrimental to durability, in agreement with [142]. Smolinka et al. [163] conducted a dynamic test on an alkaline stack from Hydrogenics composed of 25 cells. Results indicated that the degradation rate was 3 mV·1000 h⁻¹ in steady-state and more than 10 mV·1000 h⁻¹ in dynamic mode, highlighting the significant impact of intermittent operation on durability. However, discrepancies regarding the effect of cycling frequency on the performance degradation were reported meanwhile. In their study, Frensch et al. [143] found that fast cycling operation slowed down the degradation rate while the opposite trend was observed for low cycling operation, as depicted in Fig. 9. In this last case, the performance degradation was attributed to slower bubble detachment resulting in rapid membrane dehydration and increased cell ohmic resistance, both detrimental for cell durability. Additionally, the authors observed a moderate degradation impact of 1.8 mV·1000 h⁻¹ for the constant modes, when the temperature decreased to 20 °C. However, reducing the rest period in dynamic modes resulted in a negative degradation rate. Furthermore, results suggested that operating the cell at high current densities could have negative impacts on durability, consistent with findings from Rakousky et al. [142] which showed that decreasing the current density significantly resulted in a smaller voltage increase (16 mV for mode D vs 66 mV for mode C).

While intermittent conditions are generally associated with higher decay rates, performance recovery was observed by several authors when the electrolysis cell undergoes brief current shut-downs during its operation. Rakousky et al. [142] detected voltage drops of 54 mV for mode B and 15 mV for mode C when the current was interrupted after 500 h. However, comparing the voltage at t = 170 h and t = 400 h for mode C reveals that only a portion is recovered while the remaining part is lost through irreversible degradation mechanisms. Similar outcomes have been reported by Papakonstantinou et al. [147], stating that performance decay was entirely recovered after current interruption. Bergen et al. [63] also observed partial performance recovery during rest periods ranging from several hours to a few days, especially when a minimum current density was maintained. Honsho et al. [155] analyzed the performance degradation of a PEM cell subjected to an AST simulating the application of a wind profile over 160 days. The performances were momentarily recovered when rest periods were integrated to the cell operation, which corroborates the previous outcomes. Weiß et al. [140] performed a dynamic AST to investigate the effect of repetitive on/off cycles on the durability of a PEM cell. First, a performance increase of 45 mV was observed after 10 cycles. This early improvement was related to an activity enhancement of the anode catalyst during open circuit voltage (OCV) periods during which a voltage decrease caused by hydrogen crossover and accumulation, led to i) a reduction of IrO₂ to a more active metallic Ir and ii) a crystallinity change to

Fig. 9. Experimental findings: a) Voltage degradation rate for each operation configuration, b) Accumulated fluoride emissions and membrane thinning at the end-of-test of the tested PEM electrolysis cell [143]. In this illustration, temperature was maintained at $T = 80^{\circ}\text{C}$ for cyc100s, cyc10s and solar tests. Reprinted with permission from Elsevier.

amorphous IrO_2 , which is known to be more active than crystalline IrO_2 , even though less stable. After 200 cycles, a significant increase in the HFR was observed and simultaneously attributed to i) an increased electronic contact resistance due to accelerated Ti-PTL passivation and ii) repetitive chemical transitions between the crystalline iridium-based anode catalyst and amorphous iridium oxide induced by a dynamic operation. This would suggest that catalyst ageing significantly contributes to the overall performance degradation. Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) images shown in Fig. 10b illustrates the deposition of metallic Ir-based nanoparticles at the interface between the anode catalyst layer (CL) and the membrane after 718 on/off cycles. In contrast, the fresh MEA in Fig. 10a remains particle-free. The iridium dissolution and re-deposition within the membrane lead to a loss of active material at the anode, resulting in a significant decrease in catalytic activity in time. Several studies have experimentally demonstrated this outcome. For instance, Rakousky et al. [142] showed that the increase in the ohmic resistance was linked to Ti-PTL passivation and this result was further confirmed by Bautkinova et al. [166]. Zaccarine et al. [157] investigated the degradation of the anode CL of a PEM electrolysis during prolonged constant operation at 2 V and intermittent operation including IV cycling events. They observed more significant degradation during constant operation, although similar degradation mechanisms were found in both scenarios. Their findings revealed dissolution, oxidation, agglomeration, and structural changes in the smaller constituents of the CL, resulting in macroscopic changes and the formation of voids that could compromise its overall integrity. Additionally, experimental observations from Honsho et al. [155] confirmed that a significant portion of irreversible losses was attributed to the Nafion degradation and IrO_2 dissolution during the simulated 160 day-AST wind operation. These mechanisms were observed to be less active during rest periods and became more pronounced with applied potentials exceeding 2.3 V, which turns critical during long-term intermittent operation. Mitigating these losses could involve operating with

high anode catalyst loadings, as demonstrated in several studies [149, 151, 160, 161]. Alia et al. [160] showed that high catalyst loading acts as a buffer delaying irreversible losses caused by iridium dissolution. Meanwhile, low catalyst loadings exacerbate catalyst thinning and promote the above-mentioned degradation mechanisms, especially during dynamic operation [160]. However, the reliance on high catalyst loadings poses challenges related to the cost and scarcity of platinum group metals (PGM) that must still be addressed. Nonetheless, research addressing these specific issues is available. For instance, Hegge et al. [167] presented a novel anode architecture for PEM electrolysis, incorporating intercalated IrO_x nanofibers, which reduces iridium loading by more than 80 % while preserving performance and durability. This technique aims at providing enhanced efficiency, heightened stability, and paving the path for durability enhancements through the utilization of more active anode materials.

Beyond the operation of the electrolyzer itself, a high ripple factor of the converter upstream generates an increase in the HFR and issues related to mass transport limitations. This statement was supported by Parache et al. [162]. Authors compared the degradation rate of a PEM electrolyzer over 3000 h of operation when i) operating under ideal constant load and ii) integrating different kind of waveform ripple effects to the current input. It was found that i) triangular-based waveforms had the worse effect on durability over the other tested ripple patterns and ii) high ripple frequency has an impact on the overpotential evolution rate. At a current density of 0.19 A cm^{-2} , a triangular current ripple waveform with a frequency of 10 kHz resulted in an overpotential evolution rate of $96.6 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$, whereas the same waveform at 1 kHz frequency yielded a rate of $24.6 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$. The common identified degradation mechanism for all of the tests carried out was an increase in the ohmic resistance mainly due to Ti-passivation and corrosion. Meanwhile, the activation overpotential did not exhibit any reaction to ripple effects.

In addition, membrane thinning and fluoride emissions are other

Fig. 10. Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) results at the interface between the anode CL and the membrane a) at rest, b) after 718 OCV-AST cycles, c) zoom on the red rectangle shown in b) of the tested PEM electrolysis cell [140]. Reprinted with permission from Elsevier. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

reliable metrics for assessing the durability of MEA components [136, 143,147]. The increase in fluoride emissions released by the polymer membrane promotes the corrosion of Ti-based components within the cell, thereby affecting its overall integrity. Meanwhile, parasitic reactions due to gas crossover induce the reduction of oxygen to hydrogen peroxide at the cathode resulting in the formation of hydroxyl radicals in the presence of metallic ions in the feed water or coming from the stainless steel component pipelines, which chemically attack the membrane through Fenton reaction process and provoke its thinning [20, 122,168]. Results presented in Fig. 9b show that increasing the number of cycles and the temperature both lead to higher fluoride emissions and membrane thinning, thereby contributing to overall degradation of the MEA. Notably, test T90 significantly exhibits greater fluoride emissions and membrane thinning when the temperature was increased by 10 °C, indicating a negative impact of temperature rise on the cell durability. This observation highlights the counterbalancing effect that temperature increase brings on efficiency and durability. As illustration, results from Douglas et al. [165], demonstrate that the auxiliaries integrated to heat the process positively influenced the level of hydrogen production but adversely affected the durability of the alkaline cell, with a corrosion rate of the electrodes being 6.3 times higher than at ambient temperature.

3.4. Discussion

3.4.1. Literature outcomes

The review has brought to light several key learnings. First, there is unanimous agreement among studies that variations in temperature and electrical load strongly impact efficiency, gas purity, and durability. At the system level, the specific consumption tends to rise as electrical load and temperature decrease. In alignment with this trend, quantitative studies incorporating intermittent profiles from renewable energies have shown that the average efficiency of electrolyzers is lower than under steady nominal conditions. As illustrations, Olivier [20] found a system specific consumption of 7.51 kWh·Nm⁻³ during a PV-type operation compared to 7.11 kWh·Nm⁻³ during nominal operation. Likewise, Stansberry et al. [111] found a higher system efficiency of 59.88 % HHV at full load capacity, compared to 43.96 % HHV under wind conditions. However, this observation aligns with the theoretical expectations, as the system efficiency decreases with the load due to the integration of BoP components. During intermittent operation, the average load is lower than what would be observed under stable operating conditions at full load capacity. Another noteworthy finding from the research conducted by Lee et al. [107] is worth mentioning. Their study specifically focused on the ramping effect on the gas accumulation in electrolysis cells. They demonstrated that stiff ramp-up and ramp-down events and fast intermittent cycles, lead to increased gas accumulation in the PTL, impacting both efficiency and durability, with an overpotential increase of 6 %. Second, studies examining how intermittency affects gas quality showed that the purity level was affected by dynamic part-load and high-temperature conditions compared to nominal conditions. For instance, in Ref. [32], the average levels of HTO and OTH were found to be approximately 50 % lower under dynamic PV and wind operations than under nominal conditions. Again, this outcome aligns with the theoretical behavior of crossover mechanisms, indicating a prevalence of these phenomena at low electrical loads. Additionally, the time-scale of load variations also influence gas purity. Dutton et al. [59] observed that a 1-s scale intermittent wind profile exhibited a HTO of 0.72 % and OTH of 0.41%, whereas at a 150-s scale intermittent conditions, the HTO was 0.63 % and OTH was 0.28 %. Studies focusing on degradation and durability of electrolyzers have put forward the three following points: i) operating electrolysis cells at high loads and high temperature significantly degrades their performance over time [140,142,143], ii) consensus on the impact of cycling frequency on the degradation rate of electrolysis cells is not unanimous: in contrast to the collective outcomes on this specific aspect, the study

carried out by Frensch et al. [143] highlighted that the degradation rate of the studied PEM cell was slowed down by the application of fast dynamic cycles (negative degradation rates of $-25 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$ and $-19 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$ for respectively a 10-s current cycling profile and a PV profile), iii) sudden current interruption or decrease partially recover the performance of electrolysis cells [64,140,142,147,155,156], iv) ramp stiffness impacts the degradation rate on the electrolysis cells [160]. Finally, some studies have highlighted the impact of ripple factors in electrical conversion units on the efficiency, gas purity and durability of electrolyzers. The key learnings can be summarized as follows: i) an increase in the ripple factor, expected during intermittent operation, raises impurity levels in the produced gases and the amount of energy consumed by the electrolyzer for a given amount of produced hydrogen at all loads of the system operation, ii) the ripple frequency and waveform influences the degradation rate of electrolysis cells. The first outcome has been supported by Speckmann et al. [131]. The authors found that during a 5-min operation, the studied alkaline electrolyzer required 980 W more electricity to produce the same amount of hydrogen at a 25 % load when the ripple factor of the rectifier increased from 0.049 to 0.709. The second outcome can be illustrated with the research of Parache et al. [155]. They showed that at a current density of 0.19 A cm^{-2} , a triangular current ripple waveform with a frequency of 10 kHz produced an overpotential evolution rate of $96.6 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$, while the same waveform at a frequency of 1 kHz resulted in a rate of $24.6 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$. In contrast, no significant effect was observed for the tested sinusoidal-type current waveform.

3.4.2. Boundaries of existing studies and recommendations for future research

The state-of-the-art has uncovered several gaps in the existing literature. First, with relevance to all the performance indicators reviewed in this paper and for both alkaline and PEM technologies, it is observed that most publications examining the effects of intermittency on the performance indicators of electrolyzers are grounded in dynamic tests under part-load conditions or synthetic profiles mimicking the behavior of renewable energy sources. However, very few quantitative studies of intermittency based on actual operational data profiles, and especially at the system level, are available to date. At the system level, an additional point that has emerged from the current literature is the absence of studies focusing on the impact of intermittency on the operational states of electrolyzers. Nevertheless, this is a crucial consideration, as intermittent operation can lead to multiple transitions between different system operational states, which may result in non-negligible amount of hydrogen losses and additional electrical consumption, especially when the electrolyzer is operating under long-term intermittent conditions. Expanding on this last point, it is also worth noting that no long-term study based on renewable profiles has been identified in the literature. However, a comprehensive understanding of the impacts of intermittency relies on analyzing intermittent events at various time scales. Applying annual renewable profiles would, in this sense, help to capture the effects of seasonal intermittencies on the degradation of electrolyzers. In addition to the scarcity of quantitative studies, there is an absence of standardized methods and test protocols for assessing the impacts of intermittency. Up to now, most studies rely on comparing the average performances of electrolyzers under intermittent and steady nominal conditions. However, this approach raises two fundamental issues that are not considered: i) the average capacity factor of the tested intermittent profile is not equal to the nominal operating point of the electrolyzer. Thus, it amounts to comparing the system performances at two distinct average operating points, which fails to provide additional insights into the dynamic effects of intermittency on system performance. In this context, a suitable approach would have been to prioritize the comparison of system performance across different intermittent operating configurations while maintaining a same average capacity factor. This would enable to yield more accurate insights into the effects of dynamic events on the system efficiency. ii) for studies that have

incorporated dynamic effects of intermittency into their analysis, the parameters often studied include variations in the frequency and amplitude of intermittent cycles endured by the system. However, the majority of identified publications that have adopted this approach are related to durability and degradation studies. Integrating additional parameters may offer further insights into the performance and behavior of electrolyzers in response to specific dynamic effects. They may also aid in distinguishing the impact factor associated with various inherent features of intermittent operation. As mentioned earlier, the lack of studies on the impacts of intermittency extends particularly to the system level. Although a certain number of works have addressed the issues raised by intermittency, no publication integrating the degradation of Balance-of-Plant components has been identified so far. This issue, although significant as it directly impacts the operational costs and reliability of electrolyzers, remains open to date. Similarly, all studies examining the impacts of intermittency on the level of gas purity have, thus far, exclusively focused on the cell and stack levels. This limited scope is attributable to the prevalent integration of purification units by manufacturers of industrial electrolyzers, effectively removing impurities generated at the stack outlet and achieving the desired gas purity at the system level. Nevertheless, addressing this concern gains significance in intermittent system operation, presenting an opportunity for refining the design of current purification units. This consideration holds implications for the enhancement of system efficiency and overall performance. Finally, it is worth noting the lack of consensus in the literature regarding the effects of intermittency on durability and degradation. The collective findings consistently underscored that i) the degradation rate of electrolysis cells tends to be higher during dynamic operation compared to constant supply conditions, and ii) brief current interruptions or reductions promote performance recovery. Conversely, there is no unanimous agreement on the impact of the cycling frequency on the degradation rate. While the majority of studies suggested that degradation accelerated with an increased number of intermittent cycles, experimental results of Frensch et al. [143] revealed an opposite trend, as discussed earlier. These contrasting outcomes may arise from variations in the test conditions employed by the authors, the design and materials of the studied cells, among other factors. Another gap concerns the experimental approaches currently employed. The two degradation tests commonly used for electrolysis cells in the literature are ASTs and long-term studies (typically on the order of weeks or months, but never exceeding a year). However, to date, no study highlighting potential differences in cell performance after the implementation of these two approaches has been identified. Yet, such approach would, on the one hand, enable the evaluation of the reliability of ASTs compared to a more realistic situation, and on the other hand, facilitate better identification and separation of degradation mechanisms induced by intermittency, whether in electrochemical performance or materials, through ex-situ tests. These previous observations once again emphasize the need to better define standardized test protocols to characterize the impacts of intermittency.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we provided a review of 130 publications covering the impacts of intermittent operation on alkaline and PEM electrolyzers from the year 2000–2023. The review encompassed issues related to efficiency, gas quality and durability arising at all operational scales, from the cell to the system level. The key points from reviewed publications can be summarized as follows: i) performance and durability of electrolyzers at all levels of the system operation, are significantly influenced by the variation of temperature and electrical load conditions, ii) both the performance and durability of electrolyzers are impacted by the frequency of intermittent cycles during intermittent operation, iii) short current interruption or decrease promote partial performance recovery, iv) the stiffness of ramp-up and ramp-down events typically encountered in intermittent operation has an impact

on the efficiency, gas purity and degradation rate, v) the frequency and waveform of ripple factors encountered in power conversion units impact the efficiency and degradation rate of electrolyzers.

However, these outcomes are not sufficient to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impacts of intermittency on the operation and performance of electrolyzers. Specifically, the state-of-the-art reveals three critical gaps: i) research focused on evaluating the impacts of intermittency based on operational profiles remains notably limited, especially at large-scale operation, ii) there is an absence of standardized methods and test protocols for assessing the impacts of intermittency on the performances and durability of electrolyzers, iii) there is a lack of consensus in the literature regarding the impacts of intermittency on the decay rate of electrolyzers.

Understanding the issues of integrating intermittent operation is crucial to enhance the level of knowledge on electrolysis technologies and improve system design and operation. Ultimately, these efforts may promote the extensive development of renewable electrolyzers and improve the cost-effectiveness of large-scale projects in the coming years. The scope of this review primarily focused on issues related to efficiency, gas quality, and durability indicators. Nevertheless, additional indicators, such as system diagnosis and control design in intermittent conditions, warrant further exploration to comprehensively understand the impacts of intermittency on alkaline and PEM electrolyzers and to elaborate effective mitigation strategies.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Emma Nguyen: Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Pierre Olivier:** Methodology, Supervision, Validation. **Marie-Cécile Pera:** Methodology, Supervision, Validation. **Elodie Pahon:** Methodology, Supervision, Validation. **Robin Roche:** Methodology, Supervision, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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